

Data-driven Assessment of the DER Flexibility Impact on the LV Grid Management

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Abstract—Low voltage (LV) grids face a challenge of effectively managing the growing presence of new loads like electric vehicles and heat pumps, along with the equally growing installation of rooftop photovoltaic panels. This paper describes practical applications of sensitivity factors, extracted from smart meter data (i.e., without resorting to grid models), to *i)* link voltage problems to different costumers/devices and their location in the grid, *ii)* manage the flexibility provided by distributed energy resources (DERs) to regulate voltage, and *iii)* assess favorable locations for DER capacity extensions, all with the aim of supporting the decision-making process of distribution system operators (DSOs) and the design of incentives for costumers to invest in DERs. The methods are tested by running simulations based on historical meter data on six grid models provided by the *EU-Joint Research Center*. The results prove that it is feasible to implement advanced LV grid analysis and management tools despite the typical limitations in its electrical and topological characterisation, while avoiding the use of computationally heavy tools such as optimal power flows.

Index Terms—Distributed energy resources, low voltage, sensitivity factors, smart meters, voltage control, flexibility

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing penetration in distribution grids of distributed energy resources (DERs) such as photovoltaic systems (PVs), electric vehicles (EVs) and heat pumps (HPs) can cause the violation of technical constraints. On the other hand, a smart management of their associated flexibility introduces new control options to distribution system operators (DSOs), not only to solve those problems but also to expand the grid hosting capacity. As a matter of fact, DSOs have been exploring strategies to help other stakeholders to actively contribute to a more efficient power system. An interesting example is brought by Enedis with a digital platform [1] to geographically represent flexibility sourcing opportunities for private investors.

As the number of EVs continues to rise, the risk of severe voltage drops and overloading of distribution transformers becomes real. And yet, and despite the high energy needs, EVs are parked longer than necessary to fully charge, resulting in

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a significant amount of flexible consumption if the charging power of EVs could be controlled. In this sense, EVs are interesting for demand-side management strategies where the load of EVs can be shifted to reduce generation costs [2], or avoid technical violations such as line congestion, harmonic distortions, phase unbalancing, or undesirable peak demands – [3] reviews and analyses a number of services that can be provided by EVs when exploiting smart charging, including the roles of aggregators, grid ancillary services, and the associated charging and communication infrastructures.

Similarly, heavy penetration of PVs can give rise to challenges to operation such as reverse power flows, transformer overloads, violation of voltage limits, and malfunctioning of protections [4]. In the case of violation of an imposed threshold, the solution may be to partially reduce the power injection or even switch off the resource. However, the reduction of active power decreases the efficiency of PV generation, while reactive power compensation method becomes less effective due to the high R/X ratio in LV residential networks [5].

Without belittling the role of the DSO in intervening in demand response signals to ensure security of supply and quality of service, a holistic approach to resource optimisation is desirable [2]. For instance, [6] proposes a centralised coordination strategy to mitigate both PV and EV impacts, dictating the optimal aggregated signals to every aggregator by employing a mixed-integer quadratic programming approach with weights to create more fairness (i.e., avoid aggregators with a higher number of PV units to experience a larger PV power curtailment level). Addressing at the same time the management of EVs and PVs is also described in [4] for a very strict system, as it is the case of isolated islands, using a heuristic rule-based strategy and supported by an additional energy storage unit as a buffer for the renewable fluctuations. By contrast, in [7] a decentralized EV charging coordination method is proposed using only local measurements of voltage magnitudes at each charging point, not requiring an expensive and difficult to maintain communications infrastructure, but naturally presents limitations due to the reduced observability, i.e., there will be no corrective actions if the EV charger is not connected, and the solution may be sub-optimal.

In the absence of an accurate electrical model of a LV grid it is possible to resort to sensitivities extracted by the

metering infrastructure. While [8] derived them from power flow equations to minimize curtailment of PVs, and [6] used sequential perturbations and power flow analysis, Mugnier et al. proposed a method to calculate voltage sensitivity factors solely based on nodal power injections and voltage magnitudes [9]. Then, Sampaio et al. enhanced the methodology by introducing a privacy-reserving protocol during the calculation of the sensitivity factors, and by implementing a conditional parametric model that allows the coefficients to change smoothly with the values of exogenous variables (e.g., voltage at the secondary substation), accounting for different exploration conditions [10].

In the rest of this paper, Section II applies the sensitivity factors (obtained according to [10]) to different approaches that aim at providing insights for DSOs into the impact of different customer devices on the voltage quality of distribution grids with high DER-penetration. Here, II-B develops a methodology to quantify and characterize the contributions of these devices to voltage problems occurring in the LV network, II-C addresses the impact of managing DERs with the aim of minimizing voltage limit violations and II-D devises a formulation that suggests regions within the grid suitable for DER capacity extensions while minimizing additional voltage problems. Section III introduces the case study data used to assess these approaches and, finally, Section IV discusses the results.

II. METHODOLOGY AND MATHEMATICAL MODELS

A. Data-driven voltage sensitivity factors

The availability of smart meter data allows circumventing the requirement of an accurate grid topology model for the calculation of sensitivity factors, offering a linearization of the conventional single-phase power flow equations in the form of

$$\Delta V_n = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} S_{m,n} \cdot \Delta P_m + \sum_{p \in \{a,b,c\}} S_{n,p}^{SS} \cdot \Delta V_p^{SS}, \quad (1)$$

where ΔV_n [V] is the change in voltage magnitude at the single-phase connection point n and ΔP_m [kW] is the active power variation at the connection point m , from the set of measuring locations \mathcal{N} and \mathcal{M} , respectively (these sets can coincide but for the sake of generalization we have kept them separated here). $S_{n,m}$ [V/kW] defines the sensitivity factor as a linearized relationship between the former two, i.e., $S_{n,m}$ portray the effect on voltage in point n when the active power injection in point m is affected. Also, if some type of control over the voltage at the secondary substation is available, the corresponding sensitivity and voltage variation per substation phase p , $S_{n,p}^{SS}$ and V_p^{SS} , respectively, should be considered.

In addition, it is worth noting that this model does not consider reactive power due to the generally low reactive power consumption of LV consumers as well as the high R/X ratio of LV branches, which reduces the effect of reactive power on voltage. However, if necessary, the model can be easily adjusted.

B. DER impact on voltage violation

Considering the capability of linearizing power flow calculations through sensitivity factors, it is possible to develop a simplified, though computationally efficient methodology that associates and quantifies voltage violation events to specific customers. Similar practices could be implemented for other technical constraint violations, e.g., line overloads, in which case the sensitivities would have to represent a mapping from power to current. Assuming that the historical data consists of power measurements that are either already present in a disaggregated format or can be disaggregated e.g., through non-intrusive load monitoring (NILM) techniques as presented in [11], we have at every time t

$$P_{t,m} = P_{t,m}^c + P_{t,m}^g \quad (2a)$$

$$P_{t,m}^c = \sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}_m} P_{t,h} + \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}_m^c} P_{t,d} \quad (2b)$$

$$P_{t,m}^g = \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}_m^g} P_{t,d} \quad , \quad (2c)$$

where $P_{t,m}^c \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and $P_{t,m}^g \in \mathbb{R}_{\leq 0}$ are the power consumption and generation values of all devices connected to point m . Here, the consumers are composed of \mathcal{H}_m which is the set of aggregated measurements of conventional household devices (e.g. fridges, television, lighting, etc.) connected to point m and \mathcal{D}_m^c which are the measurements of flexible DER loads (e.g. heat pumps, EVs). \mathcal{D}_m^g is the set of flexible DER generation units (e.g. PV, battery storage).

When attempting to attribute voltage violations to different devices in the grid, we have to consider the correlation between consumption and undervoltages as well as generation and overvoltages. Alternatively, we could also argue that the *lack* of generation (or consumption) can be a cause for undervoltages (or overvoltages). For example, we do not know, to what extent the EV at point m can correct an overvoltage occurring at point n , because this would require additional information about e.g., its maximum charging power or state of charge of the EV. Therefore, we do not consider the EV as a contributor to the overvoltage despite its potential.

The problem is thus split into two subproblems where loads are solely responsible for undervoltages and generators for overvoltages. Introducing lower and upper voltage limits \underline{V} and \bar{V} , we define

$$\Delta V_{t,n}^u = V_{t,n} - \underline{V} \quad \text{if } V_{t,n} < \underline{V} \quad \text{else } \Delta V_{t,n}^u = 0 \quad (3a)$$

$$\Delta V_{t,n}^o = V_{t,n} - \bar{V} \quad \text{if } V_{t,n} > \bar{V} \quad \text{else } \Delta V_{t,n}^o = 0. \quad (3b)$$

When assessing the total voltage problems occurring in the grid over a specified time frame \mathcal{T} , we will from here on consider the time- and node-integrated $\Delta V_{\text{tot}}^{\text{u|o}} = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta V_{t,n}^{\text{u|o}}$. Its unit is voltage times time, in this paper, [kVh].

Two quantities are of major significance for evaluating the contribution of customers connected to point m_0 to voltage violations at points $n \in \mathcal{N}$, i.e., firstly its current power value P_{t,m_0} and secondly its sensitivities, S_{n,m_0} , towards

all other points. Computing the product of these values and comparing it to those of all other injection points $m \in \mathcal{M}$ allows us to examine the current proportionate capability of m_0 to impact the voltage at n . The contributions to under- and overvoltages will subsequently be referred to as Ω^u and Ω^o , respectively. Using the separations (2) and (3) we can calculate these contributions of the loads and generators, respectively, connected to a single point m_0 .

$$\Omega_{t,m_0}^u = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta V_{t,n}^u \frac{S_{n,m_0} \cdot P_{t,m_0}^c}{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} S_{n,m} \cdot P_{t,m}^c} \quad (4a)$$

$$\Omega_{t,m_0}^o = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \Delta V_{t,n}^o \frac{S_{n,m_0} \cdot P_{t,m_0}^g}{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} S_{n,m} \cdot P_{t,m}^g} \quad (4b)$$

Finally, we can expand the disaggregation of voltage violations to the an individual device d_0 using the aggregated power profile at the common connection point m_0 :

$$\underbrace{\Omega_{t,d_0}^u}_{d_0 \in \{\mathcal{H}_{m_0} \cup \mathcal{D}_{m_0}^c\}} = \underbrace{\Omega_{t,m_0}^u}_{P_{t,m_0}^c} \cdot \frac{P_{t,d_0}^c}{P_{t,m_0}^c}, \quad \underbrace{\Omega_{t,d_0}^o}_{d_0 \in \mathcal{D}_{m_0}^g} = \underbrace{\Omega_{t,m_0}^o}_{P_{t,m_0}^g} \cdot \frac{P_{t,d_0}^g}{P_{t,m_0}^g} \quad (5)$$

In this way, the voltage violations can be traced back to its contributors in a comprehensible and computationally efficient manner. The two-step process of breaking down voltage violations is once again visualized in Fig. 1. If we are considering a time frame \mathcal{T} and the overall time-integrated contribution caused by an injection-point m_0 or single device d_0 should be considered, we will note these as $\Omega_{m_0}^u$, $\Omega_{m_0}^o$ or $\Omega_{d_0}^u$, $\Omega_{d_0}^o$, with unit [kVh].

C. Voltage regulation through DER power variations

After tracing voltage problems back to the source, this Section presents the possibility of using the sensitivities for computing DER power variations to reduce those violations. For this, we consider the linear optimization problem:

$$\min_{\Delta P, \Delta V^{ss}} J^C = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} C_d |\Delta P_{t,d}| + \sum_{p \in \{a,b,c\}} C^{ss} |\Delta V_{t,p}^{ss}| \quad (6a)$$

$$\underline{P}_{t,d} \leq P_{t,d} + \Delta P_{t,d} \leq \bar{P}_{t,d} \quad (6b)$$

$$\Delta P_{t,m} = \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}_m} \Delta P_{t,d} \quad (6c)$$

$$\underline{V} \leq V_{t,n} + \Delta V_{t,n} \leq \bar{V} \quad (6d)$$

$$\Delta V_{t,n} = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \Delta P_{t,m} S_{n,m} + \sum_{p \in \{a,b,c\}} \Delta V_{t,p}^{ss} C_{n,p}^{ss} \quad (6e)$$

The hereby introduced cost function J^C (6a) is composed of a penalty for curtailing the DER power consumption/generation and another part for the variation of the voltage at the substation. C_d and C^{ss} are the respective cost factors. Note that the substation voltage variation ΔV^{ss} also serves as a required slack variable to make constraints (6d) and (6e) feasible in case the available active power flexibility is not enough. Thus, the cost factors are such that $C^{ss} \gg C_d$, causing the algorithm to only apply the substation control when absolutely required. If the substation control is unavailable, after optimization,

Fig. 1. Assignment of voltage violations at a single time t_0 across nodes to different DER types (loads: HH - household devices, EV - electric vehicles and HP - heat pumps / generators: PV - photovoltaic).

the substation voltage variations can be subtracted from the results, although resulting in some inevitable violations in the voltage profiles. Note that taking the absolute value in (6a) does not affect the linearity of the above problem, since the variables ΔP and ΔV^{ss} can be divided into two sign-constrained subvariables.

D. Maximizing installed DER capacity

In the following, we will consider a quadratic optimization problem that focuses on the calculation of factors k_m , $m \in \mathcal{M}$ by which the existing installed capacities per injection point P_m^{inst} could be increased while minimizing the thereby potentially created voltage violations:

$$\max_k J^D = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} C_m^{inst} k_m P_m^{inst} - \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} C_n^{\Delta V} (V^{nom} - (V_n^{avg} + \Delta V_n^{inst}))^2 \quad (7a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (7b)$$

$$1 \leq k_m \leq k_m^{max} \quad (7c)$$

$$P_m^{inst} = \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}_m} P_d^{inst} \quad (7d)$$

$$\Delta V_n^{inst} = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} S_{n,m} (k_m - 1) P_m^{inst} \quad (7e)$$

In the cost function J^D (7a), the first part (scaled by cost factors C_n^{inst}) concerns the increase in installed DER capacity while the second part (scaled by cost factors $C_n^{\Delta V}$) looks at the nodal voltage deviations from the nominal LV voltage V^{nom} caused by the voltage change ΔV_n^{inst} due to the increase in DER capacity. In order to take into consideration that certain points are more prone to voltage violations, we make use of the existing measurements to compute the historical averages of the nodal voltages V_n^{avg} and include them in the second term. A maximum increase factor k_n^{max} is introduced in order to avoid convergence issues.

It should be mentioned that the above formulation simplifies the problem of finding optimal DER capacity increases firstly by using the average value V_n^{avg} and secondly by using the installed capacity P_m^{inst} , i.e., a worst case scenario. Despite these simplifications, the results shown in Section IV display reasonable suggestions for DER capacity extensions that could

TABLE I
JRC GRID MODEL SPECIFICATIONS

JRC Grid ID	3138	3145	3210	5562	5614	5675
Total Number of Nodes	50	37	48	79	73	47
Total Circuit Length [km]	1.02	0.6	1.17	1.54	1.52	0.77
Average Line Length [km]	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
Average Impedance [Ω/km]	0.38	0.35	0.36	0.48	0.37	0.37
Average R/X Ratio [-]	5.04	4.61	4.74	5.8	4.85	4.88
Region*	U	U	U	SU	SU	SU

*U = urban, SU = semi-urban

be used by DSOs. The accuracy could be increased by scanning the entire historical dataset and hence considering time-varying operating conditions.

III. CASE STUDY

A. Historical power timeseries

The time series data was provided by the *Customer-Led Network Revolution* project [12], a four year smart grid demonstration project collecting disaggregated energy data from over 13,000 grid participants in British households. In accordance with the approaches developed in Section II, for the DER data we focused particularly on data from EVs, heat pumps and PV systems, aggregating the remaining as household appliances. All data was resampled to power timeseries with a 10-minute sampling frequency and a 3-month period from 2013-05-01 to 2013-08-01 was chosen for observation. An imputation technique based on [13] was used to filling missing data gaps.

B. Grid topology data and power flow simulations

The topology data used for the power flow calculations were based on models created within the scope of the DSO Observatory project by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC) [14]. Three LV urban and three LV semi-urban grids were extracted from the large-scale grids provided by the JRC. Some specifications for the six chosen models can be found in Table III-B. The herein shown ‘‘JRC Grid ID’’ refers to the provided substation branch ID connecting MV to LV level. Together with the historical smart meter data from Section III-A and we then randomly assigned the disaggregated household and DER time series to different points to create aggregated customer profiles. To avoid issues related to data correlation when training the linear regression model, it was ensured that the same profile was not used more than once. The power profiles were then used to run an unbalanced power flow algorithm, based on the backward-forward sweep method. From the thereby generated records of ‘‘measured’’ voltage magnitude in each LV single-phase injection point, the sensitivities could be calculated as explained in Section II-A.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this Section, we will present quantitative findings of applying the methods introduced in Section II to assign voltage violations to different customers and their respective DERs, examine the influence of DER voltage variations on the voltage

TABLE II
SIMULATION SETUP AND RESULTS

JRC Grid ID		3138	3145	3210	5562	5614	5675
No. of customer nodes		40	30	38	63	58	38
Occupation of nodes [%]		80.0	81.1	79.2	79.7	79.5	80.9
No. of nodes with	EV	27	21	25	44	39	25
	HP	34	24	32	50	47	32
	PV	31	24	30	49	45	30
Penetration* [%]	EV	67.5	70.0	65.8	69.8	67.2	65.8
	HP	85.0	80.0	84.2	79.4	81.0	84.2
	PV	77.5	80.0	78.9	77.8	77.6	78.9
Total installed capacity [kW]	EV	99.31	77.39	91.79	161.5	143.06	91.79
	HP	108.8	77.59	103.25	166.54	152.52	103.25
	PV	65.04	51.17	62.99	99.86	91.86	62.99
$\Delta V_{\text{tot}}^{\text{u}}$ [kVh]		-38.6	-16.2	-44.9	-92.8	-93.7	-30.0
$\Delta V_{\text{tot}}^{\text{o}}$ [kVh]		117.9	111.1	115.4	172.6	157.1	122.1
Contribution Ω^{u} (proportional) [%]	HH	42.6	41.6	40.5	40.4	41.2	39.9
	EV	38.9	42.1	41.5	43.7	40.0	42.3
	HP	16.6	14.2	16.4	15.0	17.7	16.0
Contribution Ω^{o} (proportional) [%]	PV	98.0	97.4	98.1	98.8	98.7	98.0

*Penetration refers to number of nodes containing DERs divided by the total number of household nodes

quality, and assess the suitability for increasing the DER capacity in different parts of the considered grid models.

For the contributions to voltage violations, different classifications can be of interest. The ones considered in this paper are spatial (geographic location/distance from transformer bus), temporal (time of the day), and by device type (i.e., HH = household devices, EV = electric vehicle, HP = heat pump and PV = photovoltaics). Using the methods described in equations (2)-(5), we obtained the quantitative results, presented in Table II. The lower and upper voltage limits were chosen to be at $\pm 5\%$ of the nominal voltage $V_{\text{nom}} = \frac{400}{\sqrt{3}}$ V.

It can be identified that the total (time-integrated) overvoltages are on average 3.3 times higher than the undervoltages (i.e., the factors $\Delta V_{\text{tot}}^{\text{o}}/|\Delta V_{\text{tot}}^{\text{u}}|$), with the difference being explained by the high simultaneity of PV systems. We can observe that EV and HH contributions to undervoltages are similar since their peaks both occur during the evening hours and are of similar magnitude. HPs contribute significantly less due to their overall flatter profiles which are compensated by the PV profiles during the daytime. The impact of the time-dependent behavior of the DERs on the contributions to voltage violations is exemplarily shown for grid JRC ID 3138 in Fig. 2, where the contributions $\Omega_{t,m}^{\text{u|o}}$ were aggregated for each point $m \in \mathcal{M}$ and hour $t \in \text{h}$ of the day, maintaining the classification by device type. As expected, overvoltages caused by PV systems occur primarily during the mid-day, while households, EVs, and HPs cause undervoltages mostly towards the evening. Figure 3 shows a spatial classification of contributions to voltage problems with power injection points segmented into 30 bins based on their distance from the substation ($\ell_{m \leftrightarrow \text{ss}}$). We can observe that voltage violations are especially caused by participants towards the right part of the graph, which can be interpreted by the increased absolute line impedance that is seen by the installations further away from the substation.

Fig. 2. Temporal occurrence of voltage violations aggregated for each hour of a day in the JRC grid with ID 3138, classified by device type.

Fig. 3. Spatial occurrence of voltage violations in the JRC grid with ID 3210, classified by device type.

The optimization of DER power variations for voltage regulation described in subsection II-C was tested on all six grid scenarios, however, in order to decrease the problem’s computational complexity, we reduced the time frame to one day. For demonstration purposes we set the factors presented in equation (6) to $C_d = 0$ and $C^{SS} = 10^6$, assuming that power variations can be enforced deliberately on the DERs. However, while HP power consumption could both be curtailed and boosted, EVs and PVs could only be curtailed. Furthermore, we assumed that substation control would not be available, treating the substation voltage as a slack variable. The used IPOPT solver based on [15] relies on an interior-point method. The results displayed in Table III show that the original voltage violations of the first day of simulation could be more than halved for all six grids, solely by enforcing power variations on the DERs. Overvoltages could be reduced easier than undervoltages due to the possibility of simultaneously curtailing PVs and boosting HP consumption at the same time. Table III also shows the amount of energy that would be added/curtailed through power variation of EVs, HPs and PVs, respectively. The signs indicate that EVs and PVs were curtailed, while HP consumption was significantly boosted. An illustrative nodal power/voltage profile is shown in Fig. 4. The voltage plot also includes the scenario where substation control is assumed to be available. Using this approach all voltage violations can be removed. Note that all of the above approaches underlie strong simplifications in terms of DER and substation flexibility. Further constraints (e.g., for maintaining similar daily energy consumption) can however be added easily to the optimization problem.

Based on the methodology described in Section II-D, we examine the possibilities of increasing the DER capacity in the proposed scenarios, while minimizing the associated effect on voltage problems. The optimization problem formulated in

TABLE III
RESULTS OF DER POWER VARIATION

scenario unit		3138	3145	3210	5562	5614	5675
ΔV_{tot}^u	w/o ΔP [Vh]	-531.55	-91.95	-371.45	-2030.54	-1712.93	-329.63
	w/ ΔP [Vh]	-230.51	-40.30	-98.28	-452.95	-586.57	-154.64
	rel. change [-]	0.43	0.44	0.26	0.22	0.34	0.47
ΔV_{tot}^o	w/o ΔP [Vh]	673.78	924.36	568.72	1312.49	1046.05	707.08
	w/ ΔP [Vh]	152.74	351.38	68.36	305.38	93.76	181.20
	rel. change [-]	0.23	0.38	0.12	0.23	0.09	0.26
energy difference	EV [kWh]	-151.12	-106.79	-125.47	-274.93	-231.97	-121.08
	HP [kWh]	622.19	608.75	508.74	573.15	591.32	681.13
	PV [kWh]	168.01	130.21	141.72	220.98	208.14	157.61

Fig. 4. Variation of power values applied to different DERs (above) as well as the voltage (below) at point 8c of grid 5614.

(7) was solved for the six grid models using $k_n^{\max} = 3$ and $C_n^{\text{inst}} = C_n^{\Delta V} = 1$. Since no information about the installed DER power values was provided by the data from [12], we assumed the maximum value of the historical profile as the installed power. As before, the IPOPT solver was employed.

Figure 5 shows the example of JRC grid 5562 and where the algorithm suggests capacity increases. Regarding the results discussed previously in this Section (see Fig. 3), it appears reasonable to suggest boosting the consumer-DER (i.e., EV and HP) capacity and especially for those located closer to the substation bus. We then ran the power flow calculations again, comparing the optimised scenario to a primitive scenario where the additional capacity is the same as in the optimized case, however, the additional capacity is evenly distributed across all power injection points occupied by customers.

The results of the three scenarios (0 = original, unscaled DER capacity, 1 = optimally scaled DER capacity, 2 = primitively scaled DER capacity) are presented in Table IV. As expected, the boost in DER capacity also increases under- and overvoltages when compared to the original scenario. However, the results also outline the inferiority of the primitive capacity scaling in comparison to the optimized scaling. When DER capacities are evenly scaled, nodal sensitivities and the locations of customers that are already vulnerable to voltage violations are ignored, thus leading to stronger overall voltage

Fig. 5. Grid plot of JRC 5562 showing the installed DER capacities and the added DER capacities resulting from solving the optimisation problem proposed in (7).

TABLE IV
RESULTS OF OPTIMIZED AND PRIMITIVE CAPACITY INCREASE

scen.		unit	3138	3145	3210	5562	5614	5675
$\sum_{d \in D^c} P_d^{inst}$	0	[kW]	358.92	275.85	336.64	571.8	509.2	336.64
	1,2	[kW]	641.1	634.2	567.7	804.0	717.0	707.4
		rel. ch.* [-]	1.786	2.299	1.686	1.406	1.408	2.101
$\sum_{d \in Dg} P_d^{inst}$	0	[kW]	65.04	51.17	62.99	99.86	91.86	62.99
	1,2	[kW]	73.0	71.3	81.6	128.7	147.7	87.7
		rel. ch. [-]	1.122	1.393	1.295	1.288	1.608	1.392
ΔV_{tot}^u	0	[kVh]	-38.6	-16.2	-44.9	-92.8	-93.7	-30.0
	1	[kVh]	-47.2	-17.6	-47.6	-96.5	-97.0	-31.9
		rel. ch. [-]	1.223	1.086	1.06	1.04	1.035	1.063
	2	[kVh]	-85.1	-59.3	-122.8	-232.4	-187.0	-85.3
		rel. ch. [-]	2.205	3.66	2.735	2.504	1.996	2.843
ΔV_{tot}^o	0	[kVh]	117.9	111.1	115.4	172.6	157.1	122.1
	1	[kVh]	134.0	118.5	122.5	180.7	164.1	130.6
		rel. ch. [-]	1.137	1.067	1.062	1.047	1.045	1.07
	2	[kVh]	203.7	232.9	242.4	335.8	285.3	226.3
		rel. ch. [-]	1.728	2.096	2.101	1.946	1.816	1.853

*rel. ch. = relative change with respect to scenario 0

problems in the grid.

V. CONCLUSION

In order to support the decision making process of DSOs and the design of incentives for customers to invest in DERs, this paper has demonstrated a number of applications that can be developed for LV networks despite characterisation limitations. For this purpose, sensitivity factors were learned from historical power and voltage measurements. Leveraging this model-free linearization of the power flow equations, different grid models were tested to compute the contribution of household appliances, electric vehicles, heat pumps and photovoltaic systems to voltage violations. Further, the sensitivity factors were used to find optimal DER power variations to improve voltage quality. It was shown that just by using DER flexibility, the voltage problems could be reduced by more than 50% for all considered scenarios. Additional im-

provements can be obtained if transformers with tap changers are available, as illustrated. Finally, an optimization for the identification of customers favorable for new DER capacity allocations was developed. The results show that the proposed locations coincide with regions with lower total sensitivity, namely installations closer to the secondary substation. When compared to a primitive capacity increase, i.e., adding equal capacity to all injection points, the optimization method results in fewer overall voltage violations.

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